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List of Acronyms

ACMs	Antenna Control Modules
AD	Additional Documents
APEX	Atacama Pathfinder Experiment
ALMA	Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array
CFM	Cold Feed Module
CST	Computer Simulation Technology
FoV	Field of View
GRASP	General Reflector Antenna Software Package
LNA	Low Noise Amplifier
MPIfR	Max Planck Institute for Radio Astronomy
MRO	Metsähovi Radio Observatory
PAF	Phased Array Field
RD	Related Documents
RFI	Radio Frequency Interference
RMS	Root Mean Square
SKA	Square Kilometer Array
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SRT	Square Kilometer Array Telescope

Applicable documents

- [AD 1] Radioblocks Deliverable D3.1: Initial Simulation core
<https://zenodo.org/records/14833539>

Reference documents

- [RD 1] “Beamformer Design Methods for Radio Astronomical Phased Array Feeds”, M. Elmer et al., IEEE Transaction on Antennas and Propagation, Vol. 60. No2, Feb. 2012,
- [RD 2] “Phased Arrays for Radioastronomy, remote sensing and satellite communications” K. Warnik et al, ISBN 978-1-108-42392-2, Cambridge University press

Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.2 reports on simulation work performed within Work Package 3, specifically under Task 3.1. This document describes the development and implementation of a Phased Array Feed (PAF) frontend simulations for the designing and characterising receiver systems for European Research Infrastructures.

The core of the simulation environment is the UFO physical ray-tracing code, which utilizes numerical solutions to Maxwell equations for the analysis of optical elements and systems. This code base, originating from the CryoPAF project of the Max-Planck für Radioastronomie started in 2017, has been integrated into a modular Python-based framework. Within this framework, one can simulate of mirrors, lenses, and telescope models, including the Effelsberg 100m, MeerKAT, and SKA-MPI prototype dishes. An initial version of this system was released as open source in August 2024.

Primary developments include the creation of an array representation module and a corresponding Field of View (FoV) analysis suite. These tools allow for the definition of focal plane geometries and the execution of noise and efficiency calculations. The system supports multiple beam-forming algorithms, such as Maximum Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), Conjugate Field Match, and Maximum Directivity. These algorithms provide performance metrics including survey speed and beam sensitivity across the FoV.

Modelling of Radio Frequency Interference and the assessment of defective element impacts are implemented to evaluate system resilience. Interoperability is maintained through a standardized HDF5 interface, which facilitates the exchange of Array Covariance Matrices with backend simulation tasks. Comparative analysis with GRASP software has verified the simulator's accuracy in predicting on-sky beam-patterns and side-lobe structures.

The current toolset provides the basis for design studies, including the SKA-mid Band 5 and APEX W-Band receivers. Future development will focus on refining the code structure and expanding documentation to increase usability for the radio astronomy community.

1 Introduction

Over the first two years of the Radioblocks project, the maintainers developed a full PAF frontend simulation system out of rudimentary existing code fragments. The PAF simulation system is based upon a physical ray-tracing software developed at the MPIfR over recent years. This physical ray-tracer includes the generation of optical elements, their combination to larger optical systems, and dedicated telescope modeling, based upon these two basic modules. Within the Radioblocks project, an array representation has been established, which can be simulated as a full PAF using the base models described above. In addition, a representation of the field-of-view, which is filled in from the telescope simulations of the array representation has been developed. This FoV representation allows getting direct access to the performance data of the simulated array. Therefore several beam-forming algorithms

are implemented, which allow the determination of the expected on sky beam-pattern including cross-pol behavior, as well as the overall sensitivity of the resulting beam. An additional large development within Radioblocks was the creation of an interface for simulation data exchange with the PAF reference implementation (task 3.1.4).

In August 2024 an initial version of the system, including the basic simulation modules developed outside of this project, have been made available as open source via a Git repository (see [AD 1]). The project is being upgraded continuously and evolving fast.

The overall frontend simulator, which includes the parts developed within the Radioblocks project, is provided as a collection of Python classes, which allows even complex frontend simulations of any radio-astronomical receiver application to be set up. This system is based upon a physical optics simulation system, capable of simulating mirrors and lenses. Simulation is done in frequency space using a fixed simulation wavelength. Multi-wavelength studies can be calculated in sequence automatically. For all modules, a wide variety of plotting options is available. In addition, a dedicated array plotting class, automatizing the plotting of the many individual results, has been developed. It is capable of providing plots for different frequencies, but also to collect them in small animations to visualize the data cubes.

The main part of this report is to show the capabilities of the simulation system as a whole. A detailed description of the software can be found in the documentation, available in the Git repository. To do so, simulations and setups are presented, which are also going beyond the PAF simulations and range from single pixel systems via array-receivers to PAF systems. They not only demonstrate the capabilities, but also the known limitations of the system as is.

Almost all plots shown within this report have been created with the simulators internal plotting functions. The exception are plots, which show simulations, or measurement data that originate from sources external to the design simulator.

2 Core modules of the frontend simulation system

Within this chapter, the core modules, realized as Python classes, are presented in their functionality with examples of their usage.

In addition to these core modules, many parameters and simulation configurations may be used to define how the simulations are set up. These are described within the software documentation, available via the Git repository.

2.1 UFO: a physical ray-tracing code

The simulation of the physical optics is based upon numerically solving the Maxwell equations. A regular grid of small surface-areas are representing mirror- or lens-surfaces. The main simulation code has been used at MPIfR in various forms for years. The current implementation was done within the cryoPAF project of the MPIfR starting back in 2017.

A position vector of the center, the normal vector of the represented surface-plane and the size define the area-elements. The solver starts with a complex three-dimensional current distribution (e.g. Gaussian distribution in a single polarization) on a predefined surface, e.g. a 2D plane or a dedicated far-field pattern in spherical coordinates. From this starting point, the software calculates the propagated field at each position of the next optical element. This field calculates to

$$\vec{E}(\vec{r}) = -ik\eta \iint_{\hat{S}} \left[\vec{J}(\vec{r}') - (\vec{J}(\vec{r}') \cdot \hat{\rho})\hat{\rho} + \frac{3}{\rho k^2} \left(ik + \frac{1}{\rho} \right) (\vec{J}(\vec{r}') \cdot \hat{\rho})\hat{\rho} - \frac{1}{k^2} \vec{J}(\vec{r}') \left(i\frac{k}{\rho} + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \right) \right] G(\vec{r}|\vec{r}') d\hat{S},$$

with \hat{S} being the starting surface, $\hat{\rho}$ the normalized connecting vector from \vec{r} to \vec{r}' , and η the free-space impedance.

$G(\vec{r}|\vec{r}')$ is denoting the scalar Greens-function belonging to

$$(\nabla^2 + k^2)G(\vec{r}|\vec{r}') = \delta(\vec{r} - \vec{r}')$$

The surface currents on the surface S (surface of the element to propagate the field to) are computed from the resulting field distribution directly via

$$\vec{J}(\vec{r}) = 2\vec{n} \times \vec{H}(\vec{r}) = -\frac{2}{\eta} \vec{n} \times (\hat{\rho} \times \vec{E})$$

From the currents on each raster point, the fields at the raster points of a following surface can be calculated, and the system works its way throughout the optical circuit.

2.1.1 Optical elements and optical systems

Optical elements are represented by point clouds (see Figure 1 for an example). Each point is assigned a location, a normal vector, and an area element size. For mirrors, the points form the overall mirror shape and define the normal vector of each point. The sum of all area sizes is equal to the mirror surface area. Lenses are composed out of two surfaces. In addition, they are assigned a permittivity for the space in between. Hence, lens simulations involve two surface-to-surface simulations, while mirror simulations only involve one calculation.

Mirrors can be calculated as conical surfaces (with parabolic, ellipsoidal (including sphere), or hyperbolic shape) or as flat mirrors. In addition, point clouds can be used to define an optical surface. Intermediate points are interpolated and the normal vectors are calculated from surrounding neighboring points. For lens calculations either the Lensmaker's equation or the formalism for aspherical lenses is used. The optical elements can be positioned freely in 3D-space to form complex optical arrangements. Combining several types of conical surfaces over the total radius of a mirror is possible, as well as changing the raster with increasing radius.

Figure 1: Typical plot of an elliptical mirror created by the plotting routine included. The asymmetry introduced by the reflection angle of 30° is visible in the x-z projection.

To simplify the setup of optical systems, the optical elements can be combined by defining distances between them and relative rotations around the bore-sight axis only. Such a system only has an input and an output port. Its simulation is straightforward and various plotting options are available. In addition, a simple geometric ray-tracing algorithm has been implemented to show the behavior of the optics. This geometric ray-tracing is in first order

intended to visualize the light-path and may be used to debug the optics system. It is not intended, and not accurate enough, to perform any further analysis on the optics. Losses can be assigned to the optics, including a temperature at which the losses are terminated.

Figure 2: Example of a two mirror optical system with a horn antenna and a screen to evaluate the simulation result.

Figure 3: 3D-projections of the example optics setup (left) including the simulated light-path (geometric ray-tracing) in red. On the right, the resulting intensity of the geometric ray-tracing is shown in false color, while the individual ray-termination positions are displayed as black dots.

Figure 2 shows the optical circuitry of a simple 2-mirror optics system. Two $f = 1500$ mm mirrors, an input waist of 25.5 mm and a simulation frequency of 66.66 GHz are used. Figure 3 visualizes the light-path from the starting point to the measurement screen as 2D

projections. The geometric ray-tracing also provides a rough intensity calculator and the distortion can be visualized by plotting the ray-termination points at the measurement plane. Nevertheless, the geometric optics are available only for debugging purposes and do not provide enough accuracy to be used for any analysis. The physical ray-tracing does provide the full accuracy (see Figure 4) and allows small deviations to become visible. In this example, the optics are breaking the symmetry due to the reflection angles and the resulting asymmetric shape of the mirrors. This is visible at levels below -40 dB when comparing E- and H-plane.

Optics systems can easily be added to telescopes and act as matching optics for the receiver system. The simulation of a telescope to which an optics system has been added performs both the optics simulation and the telescope simulation.

Multiple plotting options are available to visualize the results of the simulations.

Figure 4: Result of the physical simulation as intensity cuts. For this optics system, small reflection angles of only 30° and a long focal length of 1500 mm in relation to the wavelength provide a clean beam down to -40 dB. Below this level, the symmetry breaking nature of the optics system becomes visible.

2.1.2 Far-field data

Simulations need starting values. This simulator does not include full antenna simulation tools since it is intended only for receivers and optical systems of telescopes. As a starting point it relies on far-field data from other simulation tools like CST. Nevertheless, two generic far-fields are implemented by the class, which handles far-fields. It can generate a fully Gaussian

far field and the far field from a dipole antenna over a ground plane. Hence, one can test, optimize, and characterize optical systems by using well-known starting values.

The phase center of this far-field data can be freely positioned in 3D-space and its nominal direction of propagation can be adjusted to any 4π -angle. In addition, it provides an excitation power and an internal loss factor.

For visualization, multiple plotting options are available.

Figure 5: Two examples of available far-field options, both displayed in different plotting options. Left, 3D-plot of a CST simulated dielectric resonator antenna. Right, 2D polar projection of the internal dipole field (50 mm dipole-length).

Figure 6: CST far field simulation data of an embedded DRA antenna for six frequencies as used for the PAF simulation.

In order to load frequency-specific pre-simulated data, the class can establish a frequency dictionary. For the two internal analytic far-field types, this mechanism has limited functionality. It can only adapt the frequency but not the beam characteristics. The latter will be implemented in future. Hence, some of the simulations presented in later chapters use a work-around to this limitation.

The Figure 6 shows the far fields at different frequencies of a CST simulation of a dielectric resonator antenna under development. From the far fields given, the simulator can calculate the far field opening-angle for different power contours (see Figure 7) allow for checking the telescope illumination directly. Since, as visible in Figure 6, the far field patterns can change with the phi angle, this calculation also includes minimum and maximum opening angle throughout the circumference.

Figure 7: Calculated opening angle of the -3, -10, and -20 dB contour of the used far field. The nominal edge taper of -12 d for an angle of 78° is reached for most of the band.

2.2 Telescopes and their implementation

The UFO physical ray-tracing code was used for telescope simulation before, but within the cryoPAF project, development of a more sophisticated telescope simulator, which tries to consider all major loss-mechanisms, has been started. The current version can include atmospheric models, calculate the spillover for each optical element and terminate the loss direction-dependent. It also includes a rudimentary model of optical blockages, like secondary mirrors or support structures. In addition, a surface RMS can be included if required.

Support structures and blockages are introduced via the main dish structure by removing shadowed areas. This is a simple and fast approach to tackle the problem without the necessity of an iterative simulation setup; nevertheless, it is introducing slight inaccuracies to the model (see also chapter 2.2.2).

The off-axis MeerKAT telescope is used as an example here. It features most of the available options. The only missing part is using a surface from existing point cloud, e.g. when using a shaped dish structure as the SKA mid telescope or the SRT.

Figure 8: Visualization of the spillover regions and their temperature distributions for an elevation of 50°. The inserted figure in the upper left shows the atmospheric brightness temperatures versus frequency, for zenith (blue) and 50° elevation (red). The yellow marker is indicating the frequency (here 10 GHz) at which the sky brightness distribution of the circular plot is calculated.

The circular plot visualizes the telescope at the center, the sub-reflector spillover areas and their termination temperatures at the inner circle, the primary spillover areas and their termination temperatures at the intermediate circle and the Sky/Ground termination temperature at the outer circle. This is just a cut through the symmetry plane. The telescope simulation uses a full 4π temperature model.

The MeerKAT model includes a full atmospheric model and calculations for the spillover regions. For the secondary mirror spillover, the nominal focus position as phase center for the spillover calculation is used. For the primary dish spillover the intermediate focus of the telescope is used. The atmospheric model¹ was set up for the MeerKAT site with the data available from the NASA MERRA-2 reanalysis. Spillover regions of the sub-reflector and the primary mirror have been added and the fields are terminated during the simulation at the elevation dependent part of the sky/ground as shown in Figure 8. Hence, each portion of the spillover is terminated at an individual sky brightness temperature, directly dependent on its

¹ See “The am atmospheric model, SMA technical memo #152, doi <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.640645>. This software is a work of the United States and may be used freely with attribution and credit to the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory.

direction of propagation. The size of the spillover regions is chosen so that they cover in minimum the 2π forward hemisphere.

The raster of the telescope surfaces, as well as the spillover regions and the sky representation are wavelength dependent. When calculating the telescope representation, the basis for the simulations, one must keep this in mind and assign the shortest wavelength intended for these simulations to it. Otherwise ghost images will result from diffraction effects from the raster in the spillover regions, jeopardizing the power budget and thereby the noise temperature and efficiency determination. The raster can be adapted in radial and axial directions. Nevertheless, optimizations have been made to balance for accuracy and short calculation times.

So far, the following telescopes have been implemented:

- Effelsberg 100m prime focus
- Effelsberg 100m secondary focus
- APEX 12m, a Vertex ALMA prototype dish, secondary focus
- MeerKAT 13m off-axis telescope
- SKA-MPI Prototype dish, a 15m shaped SKA-mid dish
- Jodrell Bank Lovell 76.2m telescope prime focus
- Metsähovi radio telescope, MRO, Finland, secondary focus
- SRT focus 1 (focus 2 as well but using only the nominal conical mirror shapes and not the correct shaped optics design).

More telescopes can be added by dropping a dictionary with its specifications or a full setup function into the dedicated library folder (please refer to the software manual).

2.2.1 Behavior over elevation angle

Within this chapter, we present how the simulation is impacted when changing the elevation angle of the telescope. The telescope simulator is able to model the spillover regions and thickness of the atmosphere accordingly (see Figure 9). Shallow elevations mean that the path through the atmosphere is longer resulting in more significant noise contribution. Figure 10 visualizes this behavior in detail. The sky temperature T_{sky} is dropping when moving up in elevation and therefore reducing the effective air mass. At the same time, the spillover temperature T_{spill} starts to rise, since a larger fraction of the overall spillover is terminated at the warm ground instead of the cold sky. As a side note, Figure 9 is visualizing this behavior as cut through the telescopes symmetry axis only. The simulated 4π spillover region obviously expands in all directions. For this case, the spill-over of the primary is terminated more and more on ground with rising elevation; while the secondary spill-over is terminated more and more on sky. Both effects together cause the slight rise of T_{spill} .

Figure 9: The MPIfR SKA prototype antenna including the atmosphere at the MeerKAT site in South Africa. For 10° (left) and 80° of elevation. The change of the spillover areas and the change of the atmosphere along the line of sight are clearly visible.

Figure 10: Simulations of the noise contributions from the telescope when changing elevation. At low elevation, the sky-temperature T_{sky} is dominating and therefore increasing T_{sys} . For the SKA prototype, the spillover is terminated largely on the cold sky at low elevation, resulting in a low spillover temperature T_{spill} . For higher elevations, the sky temperature is dropping due to the reduced effective air mass the light has to pass. At the same time, a larger fraction of the telescope spillover is terminated at the warm ground, resulting in an increase of T_{spill} , which is resulting in a slight increase of T_{sys} towards the zenith (90° elevation).

2.2.2 Comparison with GRASP simulations

To verify the simulation code, but also the telescope representation, the simulator output is compared with a GRASP simulation. Comparing different simulations 1:1 is always difficult since one has to make sure that all boundary conditions are equally met and that the simulation setup is in full agreement.

Figure 11: Normalized intensity in dB of the on-sky beam-pattern of the simulated SRT-F1 (primary focus) telescope using a nominal edge-taper of -8.7 dB (field 1/e contour at a far-field opening angle of 74°). Left from the design simulator and right from GRASP. Both images are set to the same scaling (the GRASP output is in units of $\sin(\theta)$ which corresponds to -0.55° to 0.55°).

For this report, we compared the far-field response of the simulated SRT when being illuminated from the primary focus point. The 1/e field opening-angle was set to 74° , corresponding to an edge-taper of -8.7 dB. Both simulations take the secondary blockage and the support structures into account. The comparison of the unobscured raw parabolic mirror is in very close agreement and does not give any insight to possible differences. The full simulation including sub-reflector and support potentially does since more details are involved.

Within Figure 11, we compare the both resulting on sky beam-pattern and show a map of the intensity differences. Clearly visible is that the main difference comes from the support legs. Nevertheless, the maximum difference is -24.4 dB of the main beam maximum intensity located in the area of the main beam shoulder. The overall beam-width and the positions of the side-lobes are in good agreement. The outer side-lobe-levels and the outer structures start to deviate slightly. This is at power-levels far below -30 dB. Given the differences in tools, modeling of the telescope, and setup, the results of the two simulation systems are in good agreement. In Figure 12 we present cuts at $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 45^\circ$. Both cuts are in very nice agreement, showing the same side-lobe structure with similar side-lobe levels.

Figure 12: Comparison between GRASP and the PAF design simulator. Both results are in good agreement. They show the same overall structure and the same levels of the side-lobes. The 45° cuts are differing a bit more. Here the cut is parallel to the support structures and therefore directly influenced by the way the support structure is modelled.

2.3 Array representations

Geometry=UserDefined, Projected array element positions (x-y plane)

Figure 13: Complex focal plane pattern composed of several individual patterns, demonstrating the capabilities of the implementation: top; hexagonal with -30° polarization, lower left; two squared-pattern under 45° rotated and interleaved on half-spacing using two orthogonal polarizations (horizontal and vertical) and right; a Vogel's pattern with a polarization angle of 45° . The interleaved squared spacing in addition has randomized antenna positions within a radius of 4.2 mm of their nominal positions. The latter allows the generation of geometries with hyper-symmetric properties. Elements arranged in such geometries therefore have randomized intermediate phase relations.

This module is one of the main modules, which have been developed within this project directly. The basis was a rudimentary bash-scripting algorithm, allowing only the simulation of primary mirror focus PAF systems.

Figure 14: Signal chain noise parameters as used for the MPIfR extended W-band LNA (in production for ALMA band 2). This is not based upon detailed LNA noise parameter measurements; here the noise resistance was estimated from noise temperature measurements using the assumption of an input impedance of exactly 50 Ohm.

A collection of Python modules has now been developed, which allow for a flexible frontend definition within a focal plane. This can be the focal plane of a telescope (e.g. in secondary or primary focus) or that of an optics system assigned to a telescope.

These modules allow the definition of individual receiving chains, consisting of a signal chain with noise characteristics (e.g. LNA noise parameters, see Figure 14 for an example) and a far-field representation of the antenna pattern. Attributes like polarization orientation and relative phase-offset can be assigned. The far-field representation (see chapter 2.1.2) and the signal chains are realized as individual Python classes within the simulator.

The focal plane can be populated with so-called elements. Each element can have multiple receiving chains, e.g. for orthogonal polarizations. Elements are assigned a 2D focal plane position. This can be done manually or automatically by a Python class deriving a pattern, e.g. a squared or hexagonal arrangement, within given boundary conditions. Multiple patterns and elements can be combined to form a single focal plane for the simulation. This allows for inhomogeneous arrays with higher sensitivity in the center area compared to the outer areas, arrays with variable element spacing and much more. Even unrealizable setups can be created and simulated. One of the major restriction still is that the array is limited to a 2D focal plane. This does not allow for special cases (e.g. elements placed on a curved plane). Another

limitation in the automated calculation is that the element spacing must be constant across all patterns. Both will be resolved in the future to offer all degrees of freedom.

When a telescope is assigned to the array, an automated simulation sequence can be started, which outputs a list of field-of-view representations, one for each looped frequency. The possibility to loop over other parameters of the setup is currently being implemented and will be available in one of the next releases.

Figure 15: Examples for a circular array area (green) filled with squared-, hexagonal-, Vogel's-, and a random-pattern (from upper left to lower right). All patterns have a nominal spacing of 42 mm.

2.4 FoV representation

This is the second main module implemented within this project. For the full array simulation, each receiving chain is simulated for all frequencies available for that chain via the optional optics and the telescope. As a result, a $4\text{-}\pi$ representation of sky and spillover regions is stored. These data sets form the basis to calculate the array characteristics. It mainly provides the full far-field response of all receiving chains for all simulated frequencies.

Noise and efficiency calculations are based on the calculations found e.g. in [RD 1] and [RD 2]. Here mutual coupling between elements is defined only via complex overlap integrals between the individual element far-field patterns. Hence, the approach does not include any

near-field effects. Surface currents transporting any kind of energy between elements are also not considered for example. These near-field and antenna array effects must be modeled and quantified elsewhere.

Mutual impedance matrices can be calculated from the overlap integrals between the element far-field responses. Together with the termination temperatures and the excitation power, the noise resistance matrices, basis for further beam-forming, are established.

The field-of-view is defined by the position spread of the array elements on sky. Within the convex hull of them, beam-positions can be defined. For each of these positions, beam-forming can be performed using one of the implemented algorithms (see chapter 2.4.3). Hence, beams including polarization can be established throughout the field-of-view and their characteristics can be reviewed.

Each beam is assigned with calculated noise performances (e.g. LNA noise, system noise, and spillover noise) and efficiencies (total efficiency, radiation efficiency and spillover efficiency). False color maps of this performance data versus FoV position can be plotted. In addition, the far-field response of each formed beam (on-sky beam-map) can be visualized. If multiple frequencies have been simulated, their respective plots can be animated in a sequence.

From this FoV data, figures of merit like survey speed, effective number of elements, and effective angular coverage can be derived and plotted versus frequency.

All calculated data is available and accessible via the individual Python classes. Hence, additional information, where required, can be derived easily in most cases.

The simulation of a PAF for the Effelsberg 100m telescope, as presented within chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**, makes use of all these options and can act as an example her.

2.4.1 Signal modeling

Signals are modeled by inserting a tone either in the on-sky representation (astronomical source) or in the spillover area (RFI-source). Multiple RFI-sources are possible and in theory, they can be placed on-sky as well. Nevertheless, an RFI-source, such as a satellite beacon within the line of sight cannot practically be removed by a PAF. The signal will most likely saturate the receiver and even if it does not, it is indistinguishable from the astronomical signal in all aspects except signal strength. Hence removing it will also remove the signal. The situation is the same as in classical receivers (single pixel or focal plane arrays), knowledge can be gained on the frequency areas where RFI is present, but it cannot be removed.

The signal response for each receiving chain within the array for all signals (astronomical source and RFI-sources) is calculated from the chains far-field pattern directly. The full complex field overlap is gained and therefore the differences in amplitude and phase between the receiving chains can be determined.

2.4.2 Noise modeling

Noise modeling is performed in a dedicated Python class calculating all noise resistance. This includes the signal resistance matrices. All noise modeling is implemented along [RD 2]. Noise

resistance matrices are accessible and can be plotted by the internal plotting functions. The individual far field positions (on sky or within the spillover areas) are therefore multiplied by their individual termination temperature.

2.4.3 Beam-forming and beam-weights

For each on-sky position within the FoV beams can be formed. The beam-weights are stored together with the calculated beam performance data (efficiencies and noise temperatures) within a Python class.

The available beam-forming algorithms are:

- Maximum signal to noise beam-former in two variants. One faster implementation, incapable of dealing with simulated RFI and a full solver of the linear equations set up via the noise resistance and the signal resistance matrices. The solvers are selected automatically whether RFI is simulated or not, but can also be individually selected if required.
- Maximum directivity beam-former, maximizing the signal response only.
- Conjugate field match beam-former, calculated directly from the signal response of all elements.
- Single element usage, a special case that does not form beams. This can be used to get an array elements raw performance without beam forming.

From the derived beam-weights directly all performance data are being calculated. In addition, the on sky beam-pattern can be derived when necessary.

2.5 Plotting module

The array representation together with the FoV representation come along with a dedicated plotting module. The large amount of simulated data of a PAF needs to be reduced and displayed. The plotting module automates most of this and provides a wide variety of plots and animations as the result of the simulation. The plotting module is called by the array simulation directly and acts as automated plotting backend. All plots within chapter **Error! Reference source not found.** have been created via this module.

2.6 HDF5 interface

The PAF frontend simulator is able to provide simulated input data to the PAF backend simulator (Radioblocks task 3.1.4) through an HDF5 interface. This functionality is enabled by a dedicated module of the simulator, which uses the HDF5 format to store array covariance matrices (ACMs). HDF5 is an efficient solution to store large and complex data structures, while being easy to access. These features, along with being an open format, have led to broad adoption in the scientific community.

The internal structure of an HDF5 file consists of groups, data sets and attributes, which closely resemble the hierarchy of a traditional file-system. Groups function like directories, data sets are the equivalent of files and attributes are meta-data that can be attached to both groups and data sets. In the case of this interface, there are three root groups called "acms", "array" and "telescope". "acms" contains further groups to categorize the different types of ACMs (noise, signal, RFI). These subgroups eventually lead to data sets in the form of 3-dimensional arrays. Two dimensions for the ACM and a third for frequency. Another data set called "frequencies" stores a list of said frequencies in GHz.

In order to derive meaning from the ACMs, further context about the simulation setup is required. This essential information is stored in the form of attributes by the "array" and "telescope" groups. They include the name of the telescope, antenna losses and array geometry, among others.

Finally, two attributes at the root level of the file are intended to aid in debugging. A Git commit hash of the simulator and a UTC timestamp of the file creation date.

This interface has been implemented in collaboration with the developers of Radioblocks task 3.1.4. It has shown to fulfill its purpose while allowing future expansion if necessary.

3 Frontend simulation examples

Within this chapter, a few examples of use of the simulator are presented. Some of the scripts of these simulations can be found in the Git repository. The following examples are not only limited to PAF systems. They range from low frequency single pixel systems via multi-frequency systems and classical array receivers to small PAFs. They represent the wide variety of options and the high flexibility of the system for the development and analysis of receiver systems for radio astronomy. Most of these simulations have been performed outside of this project and shown here to demonstrate the performance of the tool provided to the project.

3.1 Simulations for the proposed SKA-mid band 5 receiver

Outside the Radioblocks project, for a design study for an SKA band 5b receiver (8.3 – 15.3 GHz) MPIfR performed simulations of its MPIfR SKA prototype antenna. The shaped reflector surfaces of the telescope have been constructed from a point clouds. This point clouds are resulting from the telescope photogrammetry and are reflecting the actual antenna surfaces including defects quite well. The outer shape of the sub-reflector including its extensions is modeled in detail from construction data. All calculations have been performed using a full 4π temperature model. Atmospheric data for the MeerKAT site in South Africa (see chapter 2.2) was used.

For this simulation, neither the array representation nor its automated simulation setup were used. Instead, individual simulations were set up for each elevation and each frequency to be able to vary the horn opening-angle, the phase center and the elevation. The individual simulation data was fed directly into the FoV representation to use the build in noise model.

Figure 16: Left, measured receiver noise data, used as starting point for the overall sensitivity calculation. Right, atmospheric transmission for several zenith angles used for this simulation.

The receiver noise temperature from laboratory measurements (see Figure 16) were used to derive meaningful signal chain data as starting point for the full noise simulations. Together

with the horn representation, the available telescope setup and the atmospheric conditions this allows for predictions of the final system sensitivity to be made.

The frequency-dependent opening-angle and phase center of the available horn antenna model were used to position and create the initial far field of the simulation. Hence, frequency-dependent realistic performance data, considering the actual horn characteristics, can be derived from the simulation. Nevertheless, since this is a design study only, we did not use the CST far field data of the horn antenna directly.

Figure 17: Left, simulated spillover efficiency versus frequency and observing elevation. Expectedly, the spillover efficiency is independent of the observing elevation, but depends on the changing focus and opening-angle of the receiver. Right, resulting spillover temperature, which is a part of the overall system noise temperature. It is frequency-dependent as the spillover efficiency. In contrast, it also is elevation dependent due to the varying amount of ground spillover, which contributes the most to the spillover temperature.

Figure 18: Total point source efficiency (left) and the resulting system noise temperature divided by the efficiency, a measure of the overall point-source sensitivity.

Simulations of the noise behavior over frequency and elevation (see Figure 17) show a constant spillover efficiency over elevation, as expected. Nevertheless, it changes with frequency due to the changing focus position and opening-angle of the simulated horn. The resulting spillover temperature is elevation-dependent since the amount of ground-

terminated spillover changes with it. In addition, the atmospheric temperature is also changing with elevation.

We also calculate the total signal efficiency for observing a point source. For this simulation presented here, this also includes the atmospheric transmission and aperture efficiency. Efficiencies of the receiver system and the horn have already been assigned to the receiver noise temperature in preparation of the simulation setup and are not part of the setup.

The goal of this simulation was to derive the overall point source sensitivity in form of T_{sys}/η versus frequency and elevation (see Figure 18) for a receiver with the measured and assigned parameters.

3.2 W-Band array for the APEX telescope

Figure 19: Array-layout (left), light-path (upper right) and optical circuitry (lower right) of the simulated array. Simulations have been carried out assuming a Gaussian antenna pattern with the nominal opening angle for a -12 dB edge taper at the APEX telescope when placed in secondary focus.

As a design-study for the APEX sub-millimeter telescope located at the ALMA site in the Chilean Andes, MPIfR has simulated a W-band large-scale array receiver. We again setup the simulation individually for each frequency to get full control on the horn opening-angle.

For this report, a hexagonal beam arrangement with 42 elements was simulated. The array (see Figure 19) was simulated for five frequencies ranging from 66.5 GHz to 116.5 GHz.

The main optics setup is a slightly defocused Gaussian telescope setup with a total magnification of 1. To get a uniform illumination pattern at the sub-reflector for all elements and therewith guaranteeing a uniform performance over the array, the distance between the two mirrors is slightly increased. With this, all element beams of the array hit the secondary mirror of the APEX telescope in the center. The simulation presented here include the atmospheric conditions. The degraded atmospheric transmission at the band edges lead to a strong rise in system noise temperature here.

One of the findings here is, that one can improve performance slightly, when applying beam-forming to this focal-plane array. As shown in Figure 20, this works better at the lower end of the band since the relative spacing over wavelength is reduced and the mutual coupling is higher. To visualize the performance gain, the relative differences in system noise and overall efficiency are also provided.

The slight rise in performance can be explained nicely when plotting the correlation matrices between the array elements. Within the following sub-chapter 3.2.1 an attempt is made to visualize this behavior using the internal plotting capabilities and the access to all intermediate products of the simulation.

Figure 20: Left: T_{sys}/η for the central element (blue) and for a bore-sight beam when using maximum signal-to-noise beam forming. The strong rise at the band edges is due to the atmospheric transmission. Right: Relative efficiency loss when using the single element without beam forming versus frequency (red) and the relative reduction of the system noise temperature when using max. SNR beam forming instead of a single pixel (blue). The black curve shows the decrease in sensitivity when not using beam forming.

3.2.1 Behavior over element spacing

From the behavior of the simulated W-band array, we see that beam forming can improve the performance of focal plane arrays in some areas. To explain the behavior, a small dual polarization array placed at the primary focus of the Effelsberg 100 m telescope was

simulated. To speed up calculation time, a reduced array of 21 elements (12 horizontally and 9 vertically polarized as shown in Figure 21) is used. The simulation was performed at 2.9 GHz, which corresponds to a wavelength of 103.3 mm. Nyquist sampling is therefore achieved at a spacing of around 50 mm.

Figure 21: Array layout for 50 mm spacing with 12 antennas horizontally (blue) and 9 antennas vertically (red) polarized.

Figure 22: The top row shows the beams of all antennas on sky for a spacing of 10 mm (left), 50 mm (middle) and 150 mm (right). The colors represent the intensity while the black markers indicate the position on sky. The bottom row shows the belonging signal ACMs. The color indicates the degree of correlation between signals. The diagonal is the self-correlation and therefore always 1.

Figure 22 shows that when the spacing is too narrow (left, 10 mm) the beams overlap excessively and all elements receive the same information. Any two elements of the same

polarization (upper left and lower right quadrant) have a correlation of close to one, while the introduced cross polarization remains low (lower left and upper right quadrant). When the spacing is close to Nyquist sampling (middle, 50 mm), the beams on sky have reasonable separation without losing signal correlation with their direct neighbours. This allows the array to be operated as a PAF with good beam-forming capabilities. If the spacing is large (right, 150 mm), the beams on sky have minimal overlap, even with neighbouring elements, leading to a low signal correlation throughout the array. In this case, the array is effectively a focal-plane array. Nevertheless, this small overlap can be used to improve the array sensitivity with beam forming significantly. For even larger spacings, the correlation between the elements is further reduced and the effect of beam forming is getting negligible.

3.3 Large scale PAF simulation

The main purpose of the development was to create a universal design simulator for PAFs. The previous chapters demonstrate the capabilities and provide insight to the information available within the simulation. This chapter shows how the simulator handles an actual PAF. The plotting module (see also chapter 2.5) is producing small movies to visualize the changes versus frequency. Since movies cannot be shown on paper, we only present results at dedicated frequency points.

The plots and data shown here are derived from simulations using the Effelsberg 100m telescope. This PAF serves as an example to demonstrate the software capabilities and has no real counterpart.

Figure 23: Left: Schematics of the Effelsberg 100m telescope when used in primary focus. The yellow lines indicate the opening angle required, and the cut-out areas are due to the heavily shadowing support structure of the secondary mirror. Right: noise parameters of the LNA as used for the PAF simulation. The data are based upon measurements.

The telescope simplification as used for the simulation is shown in Figure 23, this includes the visualization of the shadowed areas treated as scattering areas, which have assigned a termination temperature between sky and ground, and the opening angle required for the illumination of the telescope edge. Telescope simulations were carried out without atmosphere and for an Elevation of 90°.

For the signal chain, we use the measured data of an MPIfR/IAF in house developed LNA. This LNA was fully characterized and its noise parameters have been measured completely (see Figure 23).

Figure 24: Array layout of the simulated PAF.

The array is set up from two sub-arrays, one horizontally and one vertically polarized (see Figure 24 **Error! Reference source not found.**). All antennas are simulated as perfect antennas with a pure Gaussian far-field pattern.

Figure 25: Left top: On sky footprint of the array, by adding up all element beam-pattern; left bottom: on sky beam-pattern of the element closest to bore-sight.

Right: Individual array elements throughout the FoV (positions given in units of the array spacing). Clearly visible are the strong aberrations caused by the low F/D of the telescope.

Simulations were carried out for seven frequency settings ranging from 2.95 GHz to 3.55 GHz. The simulated on sky response of the elements is shown in Figure 25. While the element closest to bore-sight shows a decent pattern, the situation is getting different when moving to larger distances from it. The very small F/D of only 0.3 comes unavoidable with large aberrations for off-axis elements. For standard array applications, such beam-pattern would be unusable for observations. While Figure 25 shows the behavior only for 3.25 GHz, the plotting module also has created the same plots for all other six frequencies simulated, to give a complete picture on the behavior of the simulated PAF. This is especially useful, when using realistic antenna patterns (as shown in chapter 2.1.2) for the simulation.

From the simulated far field response data, the array covariance matrices for the independently available noise and signal contributions can be calculated, which can give a deeper understanding of the noise mechanisms of the simulated array. These individual noise ACMs now can be combined by adding them up. This combined noise covariance matrix together with the signal covariance matrix can be used in different combinations for beam forming. Using the signal matrix alone, results in the conjugate field match. Using a combination of signal and the inverse of the pure loss based ACM results in a maximum directivity beam. The maximum signal to noise beam can be derived from the inverse of the combined noise ACM and the signal ACM (see Figure 26). The individual covariance matrices, including the mutual coupling of the LNA noise and the reflections due to mismatches between LNA and antenna are available. They are all normalized to absolute power levels allowing putting them into direct relation and in addition getting well-calibrated results, e.g. noise temperatures in Kelvin. All of these matrices can be plotted if required.

Figure 26: Amplitudes of the ACMs for 3.25 GHz for the combined noise (left) and the source signal (right). The self-correlation (main diagonal of both matrices) is calculating as expected to 1. Since the signals linear polarization is oriented under 45° in respect to the linear polarized sub-arrays, both sub-arrays show a response. The low level of cross coupling between the elements of orthogonal polarization is due to the perfect polarization of the element. All cross-polarization coupling results only from the cross-polarization level introduced by the telescope.

Obviously, this full noise modelling requires a set of assumptions. Where possible, we included options to influence these assumptions as user like the matching strategy between LNA and

antenna. These assumptions and backgrounds are explained within the documentation of the software, which constantly is being expanded.

With the set of ACM we have all data available to form beams. Useful beamforming can only take place within the convex hull of the on sky positions of the elements. For this complete area, the system beam-weights at Nyquist spaced positions including the bore-sight beam. In Figure 27, we present the resulting bore-sight on sky beam pattern for all three available beam-formers. Since the telescope for an Elevation of 90° does not introduce any symmetry breaking and additional noise from the atmosphere is missing, the three beam-formers deliver very similar results. The small deviations from a fully symmetric pattern result from the non-symmetric array layout (see Figure 24). Especially between the CFM and the max. directivity are only barely visible. The difference to the max. SNR beam forming is more prominent, since this is the only beam-former taking the noise-levels directly into account.

Figure 27: Simulated on sky beam pattern (top-row) of the formed bore-sight beam together with their used beam-weights (bottom row) using conjugate field match (left), maximum directivity (center) and maximum signal to noise beam forming. From the idealized setup without atmosphere and without symmetry breaking by an Elevation different to 90° , all three beam formers show very similar pattern and performance data.

Figure 28 shows the change in on sky beam-pattern when moving away from bore-sight. In contrast to the pattern of the individual elements (see Figure 25), the beam-pattern stays nice and usable for scientific measurements up to 10 minutes of arc away from bore-sight, demonstrating nicely the capabilities of a PAF to increase the usable FoV. Again, the small vertical asymmetries visible in the beam-pattern are due to the array layout.

For each beam formed, all performance data (various noise temperatures, depending on the setup) and efficiencies are calculated. Most interesting is of course the sensitivity, which is

applicable as T_{sys}/η (see Figure 29). Here the differences between the beam-formers are more prominently visible. Max. SNR produces clearly the highest sensitivity, while max. directivity is the worst in this term by purely focussing on maximizing the signal throughput. The FoV within which the individual beam mapping speed is dropping not less than a factor of two compared to the best performing beam has for all beam formers a diameter of roughly 20 minutes of arc.

Figure 28: Formed beams along the Elevation axis for all three beam-former available. In contrast to the individual element pattern, the beams stay nicely defined even off bore-sight.

Figure 29: Sensitivity in terms of T_{sys}/η plotted over the full field of view for 3.25 GHz for CFM (left) max. directivity (center), and max. SNF (right). Contours denote the resulting mapping speed of 90%, 50% and 25% compared to the best performing beam.

The system also calculates how intense the elements are used within the FoV. Therefore, we sum up all beam-weight amplitudes of all formed beams and normalize them by dividing through the highest resulting value. Figure 30 shows a plot of this element usage for 3.25 GHz. It is visible, that the maximum SNR beam former uses the outer beams more than the other beam formers do. Hence it makes better use of all information accessible. The maximum directivity beam former does the opposite. It makes the least use of the information available. This behaviour also can be taken as an explanation for the differences in performance.

Figure 30: Relative element usage throughout the FoV for the three beam formers at 3.25 GHz.

Figure 31: Bore-sight beam noise source contributions over frequency (left) and the resulting receiver, and system noise temperatures (right). The variation over frequency results from the LNA variations. This is also introducing a changing in matching towards the antenna and therewith receiver losses. Important to see is that the signal temperature is much lower for max. SNR, while at the same time the spill over noise temperature is drastically reduced in comparison with the other beam-formers.

As visible in Figure 31, the overall performance has a slight frequency dependency. Here the behavior of the bore-sight beam is plotted. This is resulting from the frequency dependence of the LNA (see Figure 23). The LNA characteristics together with the matching to the antenna result in the receiver noise temperature. The loss-temperature is part of it. The signal temperature is indicating how well the source is coupling to the formed beam. This is maximized by the maximum directivity beam former. The maximum SNR beam former in contrast is coupling much worse to the source. The spill over noise temperature is the noise resulting from the spill over of the primary mirror. The maximum signal to noise manages to cancel large fractions of this noise. Even with the reduced signal, it therewith manages to increase signal to noise drastically compared to the other beam formers.

3.3.1 RFI source simulations

A big advantage of a PAF is that it can perform special filtering of the incoming signals. This capability can be used to filter RFI efficiently to access the astronomical signals. Usually this is done by placing an active null on the the RFI source.

The simulation system is capable of introducing multiple RFI sources. RFI sources up to now are set randomly within the spill over and scattering areas. Introducing RFI sources to the FoV is possible, but has little use case. A RFI source in the direct line of sight will most likely saturate some of the elements. Even is saturation is not taking place, special filtering within the FoV is barely possible since it also suppresses the astronomical signal.

The PAF response to the RFI sources can be made available to Radioblocks task 3.1.4 via the HDF5 interface. In addition, simple testing on how a dedicated PAF system can potentially deal with RFI is implemented. This test mainly shows the degradation of the sensitivity with increasing number of RFI sources. Filtering the RFI requires degrees of freedom within the beam forming, which are no longer available to improve signal to noise.

Figure 32: Bore-sight on-sky beam-pattern variation with increasing number of RFI sources. From left to right, no RFI, 60, 120, and 180 sources present. For higher number of RFI source a clear distortion of the formed beam is visible.

The system automatically can perform a simple test and provides the plots shown within this chapter. Figure 32 shows the change of the bore-sight beam pattern with increasing number of RFI sources. For 180 RFI sources, beam forming towards the source is not efficient possible anymore. This is also indicated by the steep increase of the system sensitivity above 150

sources (see Figure 33). The increase in RFI sources is naturally affecting the beam-weights. To visualize this, the beam-weight vectors amplitudes are plotted versus number of RFI sources (Figure 33, right hand side). Without change, one expects a horizontally striped pattern. Deviations indicating that weights are changing. In the last column of the plot, the amplitude structure of the weights is totally scrambled, while the main features stay stable before.

Figure 33: Left, dependency of the PAF bore-sight beam sensitivity with max. SNR beamforming to the number of suppressed RFI sources. Right, amplitudes of the beam-weight vector versus number of suppressed RFI sources.

3.3.2 Effects of failing elements

Figure 34: The impact of dead elements on the sensitivity of the bore-sight beam formed using the SNR algorithm. Above 60 dead elements, beam forming capabilities were heavily reduced, resulting mainly in the sensitivity of the single element closest to bore-sight.

In this simulation, the effects of dead (i.e. defective) elements on the sensitivity of the bore-sight SNR beam are evaluated. Where on the array the dead element is located, has a direct

impact on the result. Elements closer to the center of the array are used more than elements on the edge for example (see also element usage as presented in Figure 30). In order to mitigate this influence, each scenario is simulated several times, with a new set of random elements assigned as not usable. The resulting sensitivity is therefore derived statistically. Figure 34 therefore gives a minimum, maximum, and average performance for each number of dead elements. It is clearly visible from the plot that the statistics is too small here, resulting in still quite large fluctuations of the lines. However, it is also clearly visible that the array is tolerable against failing elements. Using only the performance data of the bore sight is obviously not a good measure here. It would be better to consider a figure of merit for the overall mapping speed of the array. The latter can be implemented by the simulation script and could be permanently added to the capabilities of the simulator directly in future versions.

4 Conclusions and outlook

This tool has been developed in a relatively short time frame and already offers a versatile range of applications for the development and characterization of complex receiver systems in radio astronomy and beyond. Although continuous improvements can be expected, its current capabilities provide a solid foundation for various use cases.

As the code base has grown rapidly, ongoing efforts will focus on refining the structure, streamlining the overall design and improving usability. In addition, the documentation will be further improved to increase usability and make the tool even more accessible and efficient in the future